

Adsorption of anionic dyes on aluminium treated corn cobs powder

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Untreated textile effluents are highly toxic as they contain a large number of metal complex dyes. The effluents discharged from various textile and dyeing industries are hazardous coloured effluents. The uptake of anionic dyes by aluminium treated corn cobs powder have been studied by batch technique. Maximum adsorption of dyes was observed at low adsorbate concentration, acidic pH and 30° temperature. The adsorption process follows Freundlich sorption isotherm and the process was found to be exothermic as adsorption decreases with increasing temperature.

Amongst physical and chemical methods, processes like adsorption, membrane filtration, chemical oxidation, dissolved air floatation, coagulation, precipitation and electrochemical methods have been effectively used for colour removal¹. Adsorption method using activated carbon is not economical, hence use of efficient and cost-effective adsorbents e.g. orange peel, hematite, banana pith, biogas residual slurry etc. has been investigated in recent years². The surface of the corn-cobs powder is cellulose based and the surface of cellulose in contact with water is negatively charged. When aluminium chloride is dissolved in a polar solvent like water, it dissociates into ions which get deposited on the surface of corn cobs powder attracting the anions. Hence the surface was modified using aluminium chloride. The present work has been undertaken to explore the feasibility of corn cobs powder treated with aluminium to remove anionic dyes.

Results and discussion

In a typical procedure, corn cobs powder treated with aluminium (as described in Experimental) was treated with adsorbate solution and shaken for a pre-determined time to optimize the conditions for maximum removal of dyes (Acid orange R, Acid Brown and Disulphine blue As). The removal of dyes was determined by measuring the absorbance before and after treatment using spectrophotometer. IR studies of the adsorbents showed the presence of carbonyl and hydroxyl groups. Scanning electron micrograph (SEM) was recorded at two different magnifications (Figs. 1a and b) using a scanning electron

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. Scanning electron micrograph of corn cobs powder : (a) and (b) represent 1 × 500 and 1 × 1200 magnifications, respectively.

microscope JSM-5610LV model with energy dispersive

analytical X-ray (EDAX). The SEM clearly reveals the surface texture and porosity of adsorbent with holes and small opening found on the surface indicating that it would increase the contact area and facilitate pore diffusion during adsorption. The elemental analysis shows that 44.66% of carbon, 0.2% of nitrogen and 6.04% of hydrogen is present in the adsorbent.

Effect of pH :

Experiments were carried at different pH's using 300 mg dm⁻³ of dyes (Acid orange R, Acid Brown and Disulphine blue As) and 1.0 g corn cobs powder. The results are tabulated in Table 1. It is evident that pH in the acidic range is more effective for dye adsorption (1.5–3.0). Further experiments were carried out at pH ~1.5.

Table 1. Effect of pH on adsorption of dyes

Initial concentration : 300 mg dm ⁻³			
pH	Amount of dye removed (mg dm ⁻³)		
	Disulphine Blue As	Acid Orange R	Acid Brown
7	223.14	221.43	204.15
5	238.62	226.05	228.78
3	265.83	254.76	253.47
2	282.81	271.32	268.92
1.5	286.35	277.80	269.04
1	286.47	278.16	269.10

At lower pH the adsorbent surface consisting of Al is protonated and the net surface become positive leading

to favorable condition for the adsorption of cat ions. The surface hydroxyl groups assume and negative charges depending on the pH of the system. This may be depicted as below :

At pH <7 positive surface as developed attract negative ions (anionic dyes) and thus removal mechanism operates through coloumbic forces³.

Effect of contact time and concentration :

Removal of anionic dyes (Acid orange R, Acid Brown and Disulphine blue As) by aluminium treated corn cobs powder with time were carried out at pH ~1.5 and temperature 30°. The removal of anionic dyes from solution increases with the lapse of time and attains equilibrium in 2 h time for removal of Acid orange R, Acid Brown and Disulphine blue As as shown in Table 2. It is evident from the table that the aluminium treated corn cobs powder has an appreciable adsorption capacity. The adsorption process is highly dependent on concentration of the solution of dyes. This is because at lower concentration the ratio of initial number of moles of dye to the available surface area is low and subsequently the fractional

Table 2. Effect of contact time and concentration on adsorption of dyes

Dye	(mg dm ⁻³)	Amount of dye removed (mg dm ³)							Highest removal (mg dm ⁻³)
		1 min	5 min	10 min	30 min	1 h	2 h	3 h	
Disulphine Blue As	100	84.36	98.09	97.55	98.65	98.77	99.08	99.08	99.08
	300	210.36	274.68	280.53	285.36	286.23	286.35	286.38	286.38
	500	307.25	433.60	462.00	468.00	470.60	472.20	472.45	472.55
	800	449.28	633.68	671.84	709.65	723.20	726.90	728.54	728.54
	1000	433.08	742.50	804.60	847.97	861.88	892.40	892.93	892.93
Acid Orange R	100	88.51	92.24	94.83	95.69	96.26	96.55	96.84	96.84
	300	244.44	266.66	272.22	275.01	277.05	277.80	277.92	277.92
	500	320.75	396.80	404.05	421.50	436.00	441.85	441.85	441.85
	800	491.76	601.18	637.65	661.18	684.71	690.59	691.76	691.76
	1000	540.40	734.52	760.23	808.50	823.71	837.88	838.93	838.93
Acid Brown	100	83.68	85.71	87.75	90.82	91.84	92.86	92.86	92.86
	300	237.93	247.35	252.18	258.60	264.24	269.04	269.13	269.13
	500	342.55	387.20	406.50	418.30	425.25	428.45	428.45	428.45
	800	450.20	581.38	618.62	633.20	644.53	654.26	655.88	655.88
	1000	541.29	692.06	728.57	752.38	771.43	782.54	784.13	784.13

adsorption becomes independent of initial concentration. However, at higher concentration the available sites of adsorption become fewer and hence the percentage removal of dye is dependent upon the initial concentration.

Thermodynamic study :

The temperature dependence of adsorption of dyes on corn cobs powder treated with aluminium was studied over a temperature range of 30–50°. The uptake of the dyes was found to decrease with increase in temperature 30–50°. This indicates adsorption is exothermic in nature. This type of temperature effect in adsorption of dyes may be due to a relative increase in escaping tendency of the dye from the solid phase to bulk phase with increase in temperature of the solution⁴. The free energy (ΔG°) change of the process which is indicative of the spontaneity of the process was calculated from the equation :

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K$$

where K is the equilibrium constant, T is temperature in Kelvin and R is gas constant.

From the Table 3 it is evident that the free energy change ΔG° is negative which indicates the spontaneous process in nature.

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters of dye binding to adsorbent

Temp. (K)	Disulphine Blue As		Acid Orange R		Acid Brown	
	$\ln K$	$-\Delta G^\circ$ KJ mol ⁻¹	$\ln K$	$-\Delta G^\circ$ KJ mol ⁻¹	$\ln K$	$-\Delta G^\circ$ KJ mol ⁻¹
303	2.8324	7.1232	2.0308	5.1072	1.7889	4.4989
313	2.7360	7.1079	1.8557	4.8209	1.6523	4.2925
323	2.4478	6.5623	1.6463	4.4136	1.5659	4.1980

Negative value of ΔH° shows the exothermic nature of adsorption. ΔS° shows increased randomness at the solid solution interface during the adsorption of dye on corn cobs powder. The adsorbed water molecules, which are displaced by the adsorbate species, gain more translation entropy than is lost by adsorbate molecules, thus allowing the prevalence of randomness in the system⁵.

Effect of particle size :

The influence of the particle size of corn cobs on the rate of adsorption has been investigated for dyes. The adsorption of dye from solution has been found to increase with decrease in particle size of aluminium treated corn cobs. This can be attributed to the breaking of larger particles which tends to open tiny cracks and channels on the particle surface, providing added surface area which can be employed in adsorption process⁶.

Adsorption isotherm :

The experimental data x/m and C_e for the uptake of anionic dyes by aluminium treated corn cobs powder and $\log x/m$ vs $\log C_e$ have been plotted in Fig. 2.

where, x = amount of solute adsorbed, m = weight of adsorbent and C_e = solute equilibrium concentration.

The adsorption equilibrium expressed by the distribution coefficient K_d is given by

$$K_d = \frac{C_o - C_e}{C_e} \times \frac{v}{m}$$

K_d = distribution coefficient and C_o = initial concentration of solute.

The plots shows that the adsorption of the dyes by aluminium treated corn cobs powder correlates with Freundlich adsorption isotherm.

The various parameters in Freundlich isotherm at 303 K have been calculated and are given in Table 4. The value of K gives a measure of adsorption capacity of mango seed powder for the dyes and the value of $1/n$ gives the intensity of adsorption. The values $1/n$ indicate that intensity

Table 4. Freundlich constants for various dyes

Dye (300 mg dm ⁻³)	Temp. (K)	K	$1/n$
Disulphine Blue As	303	1.1599	0.6098
Acid Orange R	303	0.8239	0.3187
Acid Brown	303	1.3099	0.6392

of adsorption is high in the case of all the three dyes.

Column experiment :

A continuous process employing a packed column of adsorbent substrate is expected to be more economic and efficient to operate than a batch process. Several column experiments have been conducted and results are shown

Fig. 3. Column studies of dyes.

in Fig. 3. In each case 1.0 g of adsorbate was transferred into a glass column. Glass wool was kept at the bottom of the liquid flow. The 300 mg dm⁻³ dyes solution (pH 1.5) was fed into the column at the flow rate 0.5 ml/min. To determine exhaustive capacity 30 ml fractions of the solution were collected.

The results of the column study from Fig. 3 reveal that 345 ml of Disulphine Blue As, 300 ml of Acid Orange R and 270 ml of Acid Brown can be passed through the column without any trace of dye being detected in the effluent. Hence break through and capacities of the adsorbent are 103.5, 90 and 81mg/g respectively. The exhaustive capacity of the adsorbent is higher in case of column process. This is due to continuously large concentration at the interface of the adsorption zone as adsorbate passes through the column while the concentration gradient decreases with time in batch process.

When the adsorbent becomes exhausted and the effluent from the adsorbent bed reaches the maximum level imposed, the spent adsorbent must be processed to remove the adsorbate there by regenerating the adsorbent for subsequent use. To assert the practical utility of the adsorbent, studies were under taken on column operation. Various leaching agents like 0.1 M NaOH, 0.1 M KOH, 1 M HCl, 1 M HNO₃ and 1 M H₂SO₄ were studied. The results reveal that almost complete adsorptions of dye could be achieved with 0.1 M KOH solution and column can be used for three cycle with about 14 and 31% loss in capacity.

Cost analysis :

About 10504 TMT maize is produced in India annually and the cobs are thrown as waste. So the material is easily available free of cost. For 1 kg of adsorbent 200 g of AlCl₃ was used which costs Rs. 7/-. 4 units of electricity was consumed for grinding costing Rs. 14/-. 1 kg of adsorbent and activated carbon costing Rs. 21/- and Rs. 250/- respectively.

Comparison of the proposed adsorbent was done with a standard, commercial activated carbon in terms of cost and efficiency of adsorption as given in the Table 5. The comparison shows that the adsorbents are much cheaper than the commercially available activated carbon and the efficiency is also found to be comparable.

Experimental

Sorbent :

The stalk part of corn cobs was dried for 24 h in sunlight and powdered. The powdered material was used in the experiments.

Table 5. Comparison of adsorbent with activated carbon

Dye (100 mg dm ⁻³)	Corn cobs powder					Activated carbon				
	1 min	5 min	30 min	1 h	2 h	1 min	5 min	30 min	1 h	2 h
Disulphine	84.36	98.09	98.65	98.77	99.08	93.55	98.16	99.69	99.69	99.69
Blue As										
Acid	88.51	92.24	95.69	96.26	96.55	95.12	98.56	99.71	99.71	99.71
Orange R										
Acid	83.68	85.71	90.82	91.84	92.86	91.84	94.90	96.93	98.98	98.98
Brown										

Corn cobs powder was washed several times with distilled water to remove the surface adhered particles and water soluble materials and dried at 80–100°. Then 30–60 mesh size powder was separated. 10 g of this corn cobs powder were mixed with 100 ml of 4% anhydrous AlCl₃ allowed to stand for 24 h. The resulting powder was thoroughly washed with distilled water to remove excess aluminium. The powder was dried at 100°. The prepared corn cobs powder was used in further experiments. One gram of the powder was found to retain 0.193 g of aluminium.

Batch adsorption studies :

The sorption was measured by equilibrating 1.0 g of adsorbent with 25 ml of adsorbate solution in glass stoppered bottles. These were agitated in a shaking thermostat with a constant speed of 200 rpm. The flasks were withdrawn from the shaker at pre-determined time intervals. The adsorbate was separated from the adsorbent by filtration, using Whatmann filter paper. The pH was adjusted by using required quantity of a solution of 0.1 M hydrochloric acid and pH was maintained constant throughout the adsorption process. Agitation times were increased till maximum removal occurred. The removal of dyes were determined spectrophotometrically (Systronics Digital Spectrophotometer 166) by measuring the absorbance value of the dye before and after treatment at their respective wavelength of maximum adsorption.

Conclusion :

Corn cobs powder shows significant sorption capa-

city for anionic dyes under suitable experimental condition and hence, will serve as an useful adsorbent. The raw material employed for the preparation of the substrate are widely available and inexpensive. It's anionic dye binding capacity is appreciably high. An overall agreement with Freundlich isotherm had been found. Thus it can be concluded that corn cobs powder seems to offer a very cheap, efficient and useful product for effective removal of anionic dyes from aqueous solutions. The technique may be helpful for designing and fabricating a dye rich effluent treatment plant.

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